

Introduction

Environmental changes demand sustainable conservation practices, however policies such as Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' advocate 'Specialised interventions' for endangered species and 'Additional habitat areas' without supporting evidence (Environment Victoria, 2017, p. 16 & 18). To address this, I integrated scientific research upon waterfowl into evidence based recommendations to sustain Victoria's biodiversity.

The first recommendation targets the endangered Australasian Bittern to assist repopulation by providing 7787.5 hectares of 'Bittern Friendly Rice' by 2030 through dense rice crop cover and water abundance (Herring *et al.*, 2019). The second calls for additional isolated habitat areas within treatment plants to conserve future generations of 'Chestnut Teal' through controlled releases of ammonia and saline water (Loyn *et al.*, 2023; Appendix 1). Although supported by evidence, concern arises that uncontrolled nutrient release may cause toxic runoff to which the risk was quantified through a risk matrix that defines the severity of this risk and likelihood of a drastic impact upon the 'Western Treatment Plant wetlands' (Appendix 2).

Finally aligning with 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' focus upon 'Promoting learning and guide future actions', a 'Scenario Planning Matrix' is used to analyse the conservation uncertainties to promote long - term conservation (Environment Victoria, 2017).

Evidence - Based Recommendations

Australasian Bitterns

Following a Rapid Review integrating scientific evidence with *Protecting Victoria's Environment – Biodiversity 2037*, allowed for the development of two recommendations for native wetland birds.

For Australasian Bitterns "Specialised intervention" I propose providing 7,787.5 hectares of Bittern Friendly Rice by 2030, through regulated "Early Permanent Water," with success measured by booming calls (Appendix 1). Previous strategies in reshaping habitats or removing predators, failed to boost populations amongst 97.5% of waterbirds (Garnett *et al.*, 2003). Instead, targeted habitat development is warranted, as studies show Bitterns prefer

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dense vegetation and permanent water, conditions inherent to rice fields that offer abundant food (tadpoles) and safe breeding grounds (Halse et al., 1993; Herring et al., 2019).

Research by Herring (2022) and Local Land Services NSW produced 3,115 hectares of Bittern Friendly Rice by regulating water depths (10 cm–1 m) to sustain Bittern breeding without compromising crop productivity. Expanding to 7,787.5 hectares would sustain Bitterns to retain their population for generations alongside other waterbirds, such as the Australian Painted Snipe that utilise permanent water, while minimally affecting major rice operations as land allocated constitutes a small % of total crop area at 42,500 hectares (Herring & Silcocks, 2014; SunRice, 2025). This approach aligns with 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037', policy stating environmental investments are balanced with public interest as inducing lower depths of water to sustain the Bittern population don't affect rice crop yield that support local communities livelihood (Environment Victoria, 2017, p. 36). To measure success of the strategy, booming calls can be used to monitor Australasian Bittern populations, as these birds produce distinct mating calls that indicate population changes (Williams *et al.*, 2019)

Chestnut Teals

The second recommendation targets Chestnut Teals by creating isolated habitat areas by 2027 within the Western Treatment Plant that control the release of ammonia (20.94 mg/L) and saline water (2–41 g/L) (Loyn et al., 2023; Torn et al., 2014).

Chestnut Teals, which tend to migrate during dry spells in search of food, require stable habitat conditions, however, fluctuations in water depth, weather, and habitat can reduce key food sources like *R. Turbulosa* (Norman & Chambers, 2010; Harrihill, 2024).

To provide 'Permanent Food Sources' that encourage reproduction, artificial wetlands can utilise partially treated sewage to cultivate different foods (Loyn *et al.*, 2023). The release of high ammonia promotes anaerobic conditions that support Chironomidae growth, while controlled high salinity in aerobic settings fosters stonewort development which are critical food sources for Chestnut Teal (Gerisch & Hopkins, 1986; Antczak-Orlewska et al., 2021; Fox & Stipniece, 2024; Torn et al., 2014). The growth of food sources is consistent through controlling nutrient levels allowing for extensive reproduction of 'Chestnut Teals' as it isn't dependent upon a fluctuating environment. The 'creation of additional habitat areas' as stated

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in the policy document enhances biodiversity through consistent food production via nutrient loading (Environment Victoria, 2017, p. 16).

Although this may cultivate more waterbirds, they each have their own nutrient requirements which conflict with one another such as the Chestnut Teal having high ammonia concentrations while Black Swans prefer low ammonia concentrations (Loyn *et al.*, 2023). Finding that balance of nutrients will take time, money and knowledge that doesn't fit with the policy's intentions of employing ecosystem processes that benefit all species making it difficult to implement (Environment Victoria, 2017, p. 6).

Risk Assessment

Regarding the evidence based recommendation to the 'Chestnut Teals' to induce nutrients such as ammonia, a risk associated was derived from excessive nutrient runoff outside of the isolated areas within the partially treated sewage. While higher ammonia levels support species such as Chironomidae, they can harm other organisms.

To assess this risk, I employed a Risk Assessment Matrix, which gauges the potential severity of a risk from negligible releases of ammonia (0 mg/L) to excessive releases (>10 mg/L) and the likelihood of occurrence based on hazard management (Duijm, 2015). This method combines the implications for risk alongside the probability to gauge potential complications and assist prioritizing resource allocation to prevent the risk from occurring (Sutherland *et al.*, 2021).

To exemplify this, Appendix 2) quantifies the severity of ammonia runoff within the wastewater treatment plant from Insignificant to Deadly. The risk assessment matrix conducted shows that slight toxic runoff between the treated wastewater and isolated areas for ammonia can have detrimental effects due to killing invertebrates such as Daphnia which have minimal tolerance to ammonia at 0.42 - 0.87mg/L (Gersich & Hopkins, 1986). Daphnia serves to treat wastewater given they consume suspended particles allowing for aerobic conditions that stoneworts, tadpoles and other aquatic organisms need to support waterbirds with their death resulting in the recycled water being toxic and unable to provide drinkable or usable water for humans and waterbirds alike (Esperanco *et al.*, 2025; Fox & Stipniece, 2024). The consequence of this is that we harm 'Victoria's natural capital' which is a priority

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within the policy document given we utilise over 40 billion litres of recycled water to support parks, gardens etc. (Environment Victoria, 2017, p. 29; Melbourne Water, 2023b). Given the severity of toxic runoff within the wastewater treatment plant management may include additional filtration systems and greater regulations imposed upon ‘Nutrient loading’ to minimise toxicity.

Exploring Possible Futures

Victoria’s future biodiversity conservation is shaped by two predetermined elements in rising extinction rates and intensifying climate change. Evidence shows temperatures have increased to 1.28°C above the 1900 - 2000 average, displacing native species, exemplified by the Amazonian drought killing off hundreds of native fish through droughts intensified by climate change (Braz - Mota & Val, 2024; Lindsey & Dahlman, 2025). Additionally, high extinction rates limit biodiversity conservation by reducing genetic diversity among species as ecologically unique species are susceptible to environmental disturbances (Chicorro *et al.*, 2019).

From these elements, two key drivers emerge that shape biodiversity conservation in public perspectives toward biodiversity and available scientific evidence. Both drivers guide policies toward suitable conservation practices through remaining informed within their attitudes and knowledge (Niemic *et al.*, 2020). With this, two key uncertainties can alter future conservation outcomes in the level of organizational investment in conservation, influencing consumer perception and the type of energy utilized by organizations (Wang *et al.*, 2023)."

To explore these uncertainties, a ‘2x2 scenario planning matrix’ was employed, categorising four futures based upon organisation investment level (High vs Low) and energy type (Green technology vs Fossil Fuels) (Appendix 3). This matrix is well suited to biodiversity conservation, which is inherently unpredictable due to changing climate conditions, socio-political perspectives, and other variables. This unpredictability is addressed by organizing uncertainties into defined categories to inform adaptable policy responses (Cordova-Pozo & Rouwette, 2023)

Under a high investment, green energy scenario “Earth’s Bestie” prioritises environmental accountability and scientific guidance to drive policies that boost support for Bittern Friendly Rice. In contrast, high investment paired with conventional energy creates the “Data-Led, Biodiversity-Driven” scenario, where public opinion splits over balancing fossil fuels with

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biodiversity, causing pollution in artificial wetlands. With low investment but green energy, the “Fossil Fuels Worst Nightmare” scenario emerges, as reliance on lower yield solar, wind, and hydrogen forces more land use, reducing areas for rice crops and wetlands. Finally, low investment combined with fossil fuels causes the “Planetary Procrastinator” scenario, where unchecked chemical releases produce toxic runoff that render wetlands and rice fields uninhabitable for Chestnut Teals and Australasian Bitterns.

Major Conclusion

To conclude, this white paper analyzed scientific evidence for biodiversity conservation, exposing a gap in ‘Protecting Victoria’s Environment – Biodiversity 2037’, which relies on “specific interventions” without scientific evidence. By integrating evidence, we introduced targeted measures such as “Bittern Friendly Rice” for Australasian Bitterns and artificial wetlands for Chestnut Teals that address these shortcomings. Recognizing the interconnections between species and their ecosystems, our solutions focus on strategic land allocation and habitat creation to bolster reproductive success and long-term conservation. Ultimately, this paper incorporates rigorous scientific research to encourage sustainable biodiversity practices within Victoria.

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Appendix

	Evidence - Based Recommendation (1)	Evidence - Based Recommendation (2)
S.M.A.R.T Goal/Evidence Based Recommendation	By 2030, Local Land Services NSW and Ecologists will provide over 7787.5 Hectares of 'Bittern Friendly Rice crops' to support the repopulation of the Australasian Bittern through regulated 'Early Permanent Water' and rice crop generation within the Riverina measured through booming calls	By 2027, the Western Treatment Plant will implement technology to control specific areas to pertain ammonia concentrations of 20.94mg/L (Loyn <i>et al.</i> 2023) and salinities of 2 - 41g/L (Torn <i>et al.</i> , 2014) to support year-round residency of Chestnut teals by encouraging reproduction and foraging with seasonal counts to exceed 7,000 regardless of weather (Melbourne Water, 2023a)
Specific	<p>Stakeholder: Ecologists (Eg: Matthew Herring) & Local Land Services NSW = responsible for the 'Boosting the Bunyip'</p> <p>Aspect of the policy that needs to be addressed (Lack of evidence regarding: "Collective understanding and appreciation of the importance of biodiversity (Pg: 16)" alongside supporting endangered species through "Specific interventions" (Pg: 21) (Environment Victoria, 2017))</p>	<p>Stakeholder: Melbourne Water owns the western treatment plant that manages the artificial wetland.</p> <p>Aspect of the policy that needs to be addressed (Lack of evidence + specificity regarding: "The government will engage with more non-government entities to share information... and benefit from a healthier natural environment" (Pg: 39))</p>
Measurable	<p>Measuring our targets: Australasian Bittern breeding calls to estimate Bittern populations due to being loud and distinct to find mates or defend territory Williams <i>et al.</i> (2019).</p>	<p>Measuring our targets: Achieving desired nutrient concentrations can be indicated based upon the increase in population of waterbirds as Loyn <i>et al.</i> (2023) found positive correlations between nutrient concentration and bird population through growth of stoneworts</p>
Attainable	<p>Very achievable as in 4 years Local Services grew over 3115 hectares of Bittern Friendly Rice (Herring, 2022).</p> <p>Potential Constraint: Booming calls intertwine with other Bitterns making analysing the Bittern populations difficult (Williams <i>et al.</i>, 2019)</p>	<p>Very achievable as there lie numerous technologies present that serve to regulate nutrient concentrations such as nanofiltration or microfiltration (Kamilya <i>et al.</i>, 2022) and the Western Treatment Plant already sustains 6,099 Chestnut Teals (Melbourne Water, 2023a)</p> <p>Potential Constraint: A constraint tied to this comes in balancing how much of the nutrients we release into the environment</p>
Relevant (Does the recommendation align with policy goals while addressing concerns and priorities of the key stakeholders involved)	<p>Aspects of the policy addressed to remain relevant: "Provide suitable habitats for species of conservation importance (Pg: 20)",</p> <p>"Adopt principles for facilitating good - practice private environmental investment to ensure probity, public interest, accountability, transparency and fairness (Pg: 39)"</p> <p>Local Land Services = Manages natural resources, biosecurity and the biodiversity of our environment.</p>	<p>Aspect of the policy addressed that remains relevant:</p> <p>"Enhancing biodiversity by directly managing native species through actions such as: Increasing habitat quality and extent, creating additional habitat areas and connections" (Pg: 19)</p> <p>"Focus of this plan is more on how ecosystems and ecological processes can be managed for the benefit of all species" (Pg: 20) (Improving nutrients -> Improved habitat conditions)</p>
Time bound (When should the recommendations be implemented)	<p>2030 = benchmark given the Bittern Population is 1,000 - 1,500 (Herring <i>et al.</i>, 2021) . Needs to be achieved soon to avoid extinction.</p>	<p>2027 = recommendations are implemented to gauge suitable nutrient concentrations while allowing the Chestnut Teal to grow up in that landscape given it takes 1 year to become an adult, to analyse the change in development (ABSA, 2019).</p>

Appendix 1: SMART table outlining the two evidence based recommendations based upon White Paper Part A and White Paper Part B regarding 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037'

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Severity (Increasing severity) →

Insignificant	Moderate	Severe	Deadly
The Western Treatment Plant effectively contains areas with ammonia concentrations of 20.9mg/L and a salinity of 2 - 41mg/L isolated from the rest of the wetlands to encourage the Chestnut Teal to have suitable areas to feed within Chironomidas and Stoneworts	Slight release of salt water = Too high and Chestnut Teals can't drink but allow for stonewort growth (Halse et al., 1993). Ammonia levels = Slightly released into the treated wastewater but encourage Chironomidas larvae growth	(Excess ammonia cultivates toxicity amongst other areas within the wetland causing limited wastewater treatment and killing off Daphnia capable of providing fresh water conditions (Hamilton <i>et al.</i> , 2005) (Excess ammonia of 0.42 - 0.87mg/L is the maximum acceptable amount according to (Gersich & Hopkins, 1986)) alongside high salinity leaving 'Chironomidae' incapable of surviving which is a crucial food source for Chestnut Teal (Cartier <i>et al.</i> , 2011; O'Connor <i>et al.</i> , 2013))	(Induction of excess nutrients results in the Western Treatment Plant remaining inhabitable for Chestnut Teal due to the wetland being entirely anaerobic with no food production. The salinity drastically exceeds 41mg/L and the ammonia concentrations are much higher than 20.9mg/L.

Likelihood (Decreased Likelihood) ↓

Certain	Low Risk (2)	Potential Risk (5)	Severe Risk (9)	Severe Risk (10)
Likely	Low Risk (3)	Potential Risk (4)	Severe Risk (9)	Severe Risk (9)
Unlikely	Low Risk (3)	Low Risk (3)	High Risk (8)	Severe Risk (9)
Rare	Low Risk (2)	Low Risk (3)	High Risk (7)	High Risk (7)

Appendix 2: Risk Assessment Matrix detailing the risk of excessive release of ammonia, salinity tied to partially treated sewage regarding the evidence based recommendation: By 2027, the Western Treatment Plant will implement technology to control specific areas to pertain ammonia concentrations of 20.94mg/L (Loyn *et al.* 2023) and salinities of 2 - 41g/L (Torn *et al.*, 2014) to support year-round residency of Chestnut teals by encouraging reproduction and foraging with seasonal counts to exceed 7,000 regardless of weather (Melbourne Water, 2023a). Risk assessment is scaled numerically for the severity of the risk from 1 - 10 with 1 - 3 indicating minimal release of nutrient runoff into surrounding areas, 4 - 6 pertaining a potential risk requiring monitoring of the areas allocated to ensure minimal excessive nutrient, 7 - 8 indicates a high risk requiring direct intervention, policies, training and restriction regarding the amount of nutrients induced within the area and between 9 - 10 indicates a toxic runoff to the point where remediation is not an option with the surrounding areas pertaining toxicity levels too high to sustain the Chestnut Teal.

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How much are organisations going to invest within resources, capital and time across Victoria to avidly seek the conservation of our natural resources and environment?

What types of energy will predominate our industries, technology and how will we utilise our natural resources within our environment?

	Finance and capital is directed towards conservation and protection strategies for the natural environment through the guidance of scientific knowledge (High Investment)	Investment doesn't support the environment and scientific development leading to unsustainable practices for flora and fauna (Low Investment)
Movement towards green energy/technology (Green Energy/Tech nology)	<p>The Earth's Bestie</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industries work together to sustain production through hydrogen fuels, solar energy etc. and form communication networks amongst scientists to conserve animals - Government policies prioritise environmental accountability leading to forced investment potentially creating divide if not justified. (Carbon Taxing in Australia, that created divide due to pricing and investment requirements) - Scientific evidence is crucial to justify changes regarding conservation. - The reformation of public practices and emphasis upon scientific knowledge reshapes perspective to prioritise remaining 'Environmentally conscious'. - Resource extraction = stringent requiring investment and justification to be used. 	<p>Fossil Fuels Worst Nightmare</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Green Energy/Technologies implement solar, wind and hydrogen fuels using excessive land to meet the same energy as conventional fuels. - Meeting our energy demands -> populations of native animals, vegetation declining through the destruction of the environment deemed 'unnecessary'. - Initiatives serve to integrate 'Green Technology' within the local communities to alter public perception (Eg: Small-scale renewable energy scheme where local communities were rewarded for utilising solar panels through monetary reward to improve sustainable energy use) - Government regulation regarding 'Green Technology' = necessary to conserve flora + fauna
Reliance upon fossil fuels (Conventional Energy/Tech nology)	<p>Data-led, Biodiversity-driven</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industries rely upon fossil fuels like oil, coal etc. causing climate change through greenhouse gases - Conservation of flora and fauna is inconsistent due to excess pollution in the ozone layer that drastically alters the environmental conditions through climate change (Eg: Gradual melting of glaciers/sea ice -> displacement of polar bears within the environment.) - Public riots, coalitions + groups arise to advocate for balancing fossil fuel usage to decrease climate change and such as 'The Climate Council'. - Media companies illustrate concerns and encourage public participation to halt conventional fuels. Concerns arise from potential 'Media Bias', 'Misinformation' spread regarding the 'Climate Change' and 'Fossil fuels'. 	<p>Planetary Procrastinator</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industries manufacture goods through fossil fuels with minimal regard to the environment - Sewage, plastic, toxic waste etc. release into the environment, endangering the ecosystem (Eg: 'Great Barrier Reef' with excess plastic destroying the coral) - Endangered species that need external support (Eg: Australasian Bittern) will die through less provision of suitable habitats through prioritising economic efficiency. - Quality of air drastically reduces through less flora and inconsistent growth conditions that make supporting the natural environment impossible. - Synthetic production and technology predominates flora and fauna growth due to an inability to sustain natural life.

Appendix 3: 2x2 Scenario Planning Matrix regarding both 'Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037' & avidly supporting the sustainment of the Australasian Bittern population